

ORGANIC ACID—Fe COMPLEX AS A DISTURBING FACTOR IN THE TITRIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF ASCORBIC ACID.

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Organic acid—Fe⁺⁺ complexes can act as disturbing factors in the estimation of ascorbic acid with Tillmans' reagent (2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol) even in the acid medium. Quantitative investigation of reducing properties of some of these acid—Fe⁺⁺ complexes has been made. The method of precipitation with mercuric acetate cannot remove citric acid—Fe⁺⁺ completely (elimination = 87%).

Within a year after the introduction of 2 : 6-dichlorophenolindophenol for estimating ascorbic acid in tissue and vegetable extracts by Tillmans, Hirsch and Hirsch (*Z. Lebens*, 1932, 63, 1) it was pointed out that the presence of sulphhydryl compounds, such as cysteine and glutathione interfered with the estimation in the neutral medium at which the titration was usually made. Birch, Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 590; Wolff, Van Eckelen and Emmerie (*Acta Brev. neerl. Physiol.*, 1933, 9, 44) conducted the estimation in the acid medium and did away with the disturbing effect of glutathione and ferrous salts which reduce the indicator in neutral medium. But cysteine, ergothione and tannins still exerted their influence in reducing the reagent. Emmerie (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 268) and Emmerie and Van Eckelen (*Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1153) developed the method of eliminating these disturbing factors present in the trichloroacetic acid extract of the tissues, by precipitation with mercuric acetate. Proteins, which were another source of error in the titration method, were already removed while extracting the tissues with trichloroacetic acid. It was also recorded in the same year (Van Eckelen, *loc. cit.*) that besides these, other reducing substances such as thiosulphates in urine caused marked deviation from the correct result if they were not eliminated (*cf.* Heinemann, *Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 2299). Van Eckelen has shown that mercuric acetate is quite efficient in precipitating thiosulphates and other disturbing factors.

The effect of ferrous salts which were also found to interfere with the estimation of ascorbic acid by Tillmans' reagent was supposed to be eliminated if the titration was carried out in acid medium (*cf.* Birch, *loc. cit.*, Wolff *et al*, *loc. cit.*) and Svrbely and Szent-Györgyi (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 279), but results obtained by us are very striking. It has been found that though the ferrous salts of inorganic acids (*e.g.* ferrous sulphate)

have little or practically no influence on the reduction of the indophenol dye in acid medium, ferrous sulphate in presence of organic acids, both dibasic and hydroxy acids, or in other words organic acid—Fe^{II} complex possesses a strong reducing action on the indicator, even in acid medium.

The present communication deals with the quantitative estimation of the reducing action of some of the organic acid—Fe^{II} complexes on the Tillmans' reagent. The degree of elimination of this class of reducing complexes by Emmerie's reagent will also be discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The indicator solution was made and standardised according to Harris and Ray (*Biochem. J.*, 1933, 27, 303). The indicator solution (5 c.c.) was found equivalent to 0.4134 mg. of ascorbic acid. 0.5 C.c. of acetic acid was added to the dye before titration as recommended by Ghosh and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30).

Experiments were carried out with the dicarboxylic acids *viz.*, oxalic, malonic and succinic and the hydroxy acids *viz.*, malic, tartaric and citric, which are generally present in large quantities in fruits and vegetables.

It will be seen from Table I that as the number of carbon atoms in the dibasic acids increases the reducing capacity of the acid—Fe^{II} complex diminishes. Succinic acid—Fe^{II} has practically no reducing property at all. Oxalic acid at the concentration of *M/5* forms insoluble ferrous salt with *M/5* ferrous sulphate; hence a concentration of *M/50* was selected for this acid. It will also be seen that of the three hydroxy acid—Fe^{II} complexes, citric acid—Fe^{II} has the greatest reducing property and malic acid—Fe^{II} the least and it thus appears that in the hydroxy acids the reducing power is directly proportional to the molecular weight of the acids. Blank experiments were always carried out.

It is to be noted that neither the acids nor ferrous sulphate in aqueous solution taken separately, exert any appreciable reducing action on the dye. The reducing action of the acid—Fe^{II} complexes is shown in Table I. The strength of the ferrous sulphate solution, which was always the same as that of the acids, was always *M/5* except in the case of oxalic acid where a solution of *M/50* was used.

It will appear from Table I that when the organic acid and the ferrous salt are taken in equivalent amounts the mixture possesses the greatest reducing properties. Organic acids as well as iron are widely distributed in the vegetable kingdom. It is possible that the reducing action of plant and fruit juices on 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol may, to

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some extent at least, be due to the presence of organic acid—Fe^{II} complexes as mentioned above. It is absolutely necessary to eliminate all these disturbing factors before ascorbic acid can be accurately determined by Tillmans' method.

TABLE I.

(1 C.c. indicator $\equiv$ 0.0827 mg. of ascorbic acid).

Proportion of the vol. of organic acid : ferrous sulphate in the solution.	Vol. of acid—Fe ^{II} complex $\equiv$ 5 c.c. indicator.				
	Oxalic.	Malonic	Malic.	Tartaric.	Citric.
9 : 1	4.4 c.c.	3.4 c.c.	6.2 c.c.	4.5 c.c.	2.0 c.c.
8 : 2	3.4	2.6	5.4	3.6	1.5
7 : 3	2.6	2.1	4.8	3.0	1.2
6 : 4	2.4	2.0	4.2	2.6	1.1
5 : 5	2.3	1.8	3.8	2.4	1.0
4 : 6	2.4	2.1	4.8	2.8	1.1
3 : 7	4.1	2.6	5.9	3.4	1.2
2 : 8	6.6	3.3	6.8	4.1	1.5
1 : 9	12.25	4.6	7.8	4.7	1.9

Experiments were then carried out with a view to remove these acid—Fe^{II} reducing complexes by precipitation with mercuric acetate. Results are shown in the following table.

TABLE II.

(1 C.c. indicator $\equiv$ 0.0827 mg. of ascorbic acid).

100 C.c. solution containing.	Vol. $\approx$ 2 c.c. of indicator.	Total vol. of indicator $\approx$ 100 c.c. solution.	Equiv. weight of ascorbic acid.
M/5-citric acid (5 c. c.) and 5 c.c. ferrous sulphate (M/5)	2.6 c.c.	77.0 c.c.	6.37 mg.
M/5 citric acid (5 c.c.) and 5 c.c. ferrous sulphate treated with mercuric acetate and hydrogen sulphide	20.0	10.0	0.83

It appears from Table II that only 87% of the reducing complex are eliminated by treatment with mercuric acetate.

Thus it is evident that due to the presence of various reducing factors, the titrimetric method of Tillmans for estimating ascorbic acid cannot give very accurate results whatever precautions are taken for eliminating them. A recent observation by Miller and Robbins (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 1) also shows that results with mercuric acetate are unsatisfactory.